

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: JOLEM****FIRST NAME: MWANJE****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The Author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago footnote (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The Author did use Zotero to insert references

The Author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10 pro)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **What is the first step in ensuring your essay is well-structured and clearly argued?**

- Writing the conclusion to summarize your points.
- Starting early to allow time for research and revisions.¹**
- Choosing a font and layout for your paper.
- Writing the introduction to grab the reader's attention.

2. **Which of the following is crucial to avoid plagiarism in your academic writing?**

- Using as many direct quotes as possible.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 4th ed.* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7.

Following a style guide for proper citation and referencing.²

Writing in American English only.

Avoiding the use of digital sources for research.

3. **What are the four parts of a response paper at EUCLID?**

Introduction, Body, Conclusion, Bibliography.

Summary of the material studied, Your reaction to the study material, The conclusion, References.³

Abstract, Literature Review, Methodology, Results.

Thesis Statement, Argument Development, Counterarguments, Conclusion.

4. **Which tool is recommended for managing bibliographies in the dissertation writing process?**

Microsoft Excel.

Zotero.⁴

Microsoft PowerPoint.

Google Scholar.

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 52.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Gulma Kabiru, *How to Write a Response Paper (RP)* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 2–12.

⁴ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 4.

5. **Why is careful planning and time management emphasized in the dissertation process?**
- To allow more time for social activities.
 - To make the dissertation shorter and less detailed.
 - To impress the dissertation committee with speed rather than quality.
 - To ensure the dissertation is completed before the deadline, avoiding unnecessary stress.⁵**
6. **What is the primary purpose of asking effective questions in the research process?**
- To limit the scope of the research to a manageable size.
 - To identify a unique and significant research problem or question.⁶**
 - To make the research process easier for the researcher.
 - To ensure the research can be completed quickly.
7. **When compiling a list of sources, what is most crucial to ensure proper citation and avoid plagiarism?**
- Using as many sources as possible to appear well-researched.
 - Summarizing each source to make it easier to remember.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 52.

⁶ Turabian, 17.

Choosing sources that only agree with the researcher's hypothesis.

Recording complete bibliographical information for each source.⁷

8. **What is the most effective strategy for planning the first draft of a research paper?**

Writing the introduction first to guide the rest of the paper.

Focusing solely on gathering as much evidence as possible before writing.

Planning a draft that meets the readers' needs, including a logical order and clear argument structure.⁸

Starting with the conclusion to make sure the research objectives are met.

9. **What is the primary purpose of operationalizing variables in both quantitative and qualitative research?**

To ensure that the research questions are clearly defined and measurable.

To identify the best statistical methods for data analysis.

To determine the sample size for the study.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 43.

⁸ James P. Sampson, *Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research, Second Edition* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 10.

To measure variables using instruments or focus group questions for accurate data collection.⁹

10. **To fill pages and meet the word count requirements for the dissertation.**

To fill pages and meet the word count requirements for the dissertation.

To provide a critical analysis of existing literature, align it with research questions, and establish the research gap.¹⁰

To list all the books and articles the researcher has read during the study.

To impress the dissertation committee with the number of sources reviewed.

⁹ Sampson, 43.

¹⁰ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 191.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.